

MODERN PEDAGOGICAL METHODS TO IMPROVE LANGUAGE LEARNING

Annotation: The article contains information about the new pedagogical method "Zimmarvina" created to facilitate students' learning of foreign languages.

The results of experiments and observations about the efficiency and ease of use of this created method are highlighted.

Keywords: pedagogical technology, "step by step", method, effect, stage, my interests, what I am, future me, my state.

In recent years, the need for languages and language learning has been increasing in the world. Some people need to learn a language for work, some for study, and some for leisure.

As philologists, we teach the Russian language in many faculties and in various directions at the level of Bahkhaia State University. In the process of work, we face various difficulties, more precisely, there were times when we had difficulties with students regarding language teaching.

We mainly teach Russian language and literature to non-specialists, i.e., when the language is different, and it is not always satisfactory.

Many new pedagogical technologies are currently being developed in our country, and not all of them can be used in the language learning process. Therefore, based on our scientific research and experience, we classify the students in the groups we teach (we divide them into groups according to the level of language proficiency).

In our scientific research, we developed the "Zimmarvina" ("step by

Shalipova Ekaterina Gulyamovna
Lecturer at the Faculty of Philology,
Bahkhaia State University
Khalidzeva Ekaterina Fakhimovna
Lecturer at the Faculty of Philology,
Bahkhaia State University

step") pedagogical technology. Not all pedagogues use this pedagogical technology in the same way, it can be used differently depending on their pedagogical skills.

This pedagogical technology consists of the following stages: introduction (who I am, my interests, my family, my hobbies, my ideal, my future self). At the first stage, the student tells about his/her name, age, field of study. Then the student is required to fully pronounce my name, my surname, I study in this direction, I am a student of this course. The fact that the student tells all the information about himself in full allows him to increase his vocabulary and pronounce words correctly.

Before proceeding to the second stage, the student should repeat the given text, that is, make sure that the information from the first stage is complete and without errors. Now he can go to the second stage.

The second stage is my interests, the student lists his interests one by one. Tells the positive aspects of these interests, which gives insight into what these interests can bring to the student. Before proceeding to the third stage, the student is required to mention the information of the first and second stages.

In the third stage, the student counts whether the family is big or small, how many people there are in the family, sisters, brothers, other members of the family, father, mother, grandparents, and close relatives in the family.

The fourth stage is my hobby. The student tells his hobbies or activities, he must say when the hobby appeared and changed.

My ideal or ideals. At this stage, the student tells about his ideals, here he becomes interested in them and why he considers him or them as ideal, and about the role of his ideals in his life.

And finally, the sixth stage. I'm in the future. the student tells how he imagines himself in the future by his profession.

When using this method, it is necessary to classify the students of the group. After one month, the student will be able to give information about himself, his interests and ideals, and his family in a foreign language and in Russian.

During our scientific observations, this method has been proven to be effective. My colleague Khatunava Ekaterina Felatovna helped a lot in applying the method, this pedagogical method paid off, our students could talk about themselves in one month, and in six months they could speak in Russian.

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